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DIASPORIC SENSIBILITY IN THE SELECT NOVELS OF KAMALA MARKANDAYA

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Abstract

Diaspora Theory which emerged in the second half of the 20th century has its influence on literature across most of the languages around the world. It is also popularly known as Emigrant or Diasporic Literature. Diasporas include concepts such as migration, individuality, and isolation, which have attracted many Indian writers who have reflected these concepts in their writings. This paper is an attempt to analyze the diasporic sensibility in the select novels of Kamala Markandaya like *Nectar in a Sieve*, *Possession*, *Nowhere Man* and *A Handful of Rice*. A migrant, who relocates from the motherland to a foreign country, becomes an outsider in the foreign land and this estrangement affects the person's identity and psychosomatic peace thereby impacting the existential status. Indians started getting affiliated with migration during the pre-independence period and England was the fairyland for many of them. That was the period of colonialism and many countries around the world were colonies of the British. The writers who had migrated over a while, to England faced the effects of diaspora which were penned down through the characters in their novels.

Keywords: Diaspora theory, diasporic sensibility, migration, isolation, culture, identity.

"Diaspora" the term takes its origination back in the 8th century BC. The roots of this term are from the Greek language and refer to migration or colonization. The term was used to express the experience faced by Jews while migrating to various countries due to invasions back in the 8th century BC. The term was used by Jews to express the feeling of connectedness. To quote Baumann's words, "in the western common knowledge, the notion of exile is predominantly bound to the experience of the Jewish people in the first millennium BCE". One such example is the land of Babylonia where Jews were in captivity for 40 years, from 587 to 538 BCE. Once freed, some of them immigrated to various places while the rest were forcefully deported. They were so dispersed and were termed as "diaspora". Since its origination, the original definition of diaspora has got transformed and stretched out to cover wider themes, in due course.

From the Jewish perspective, the term diaspora has a theological dimension. The Jews are scattered and this term refers to "Bringing them together" at the end time, by the grace of God. Jews strongly believed that their captivity in Babylon was due to their disobedience to the commandments of the Torah, as a punishment from God. Countries around the world have seen a substantial number of successful and well-established Jews, but still, they consider themselves as outsiders since they are awaiting their final gathering in Jerusalem as promised by God. The term diaspora slowly vanished after the 4th century since Christianity became the state religion of the Roman Empire and reappeared after a millennium, to be precise in the sixteenth century referring to Protestants living in Catholic territory or vice versa.

Though the term originated and revolved around Jews, since the 19th century, predominantly the term was used around interstate migration. However, the term diaspora does always associated with a relative newcomer or an outsider into a well-established nation with a defined society or population.

Starting around the religious origin, the diasporas started covering political, economics, and more recently climate-related issues.

The concept of immigration or relocation is embraced by individuals, but diaspora is a collective dimension since Diasporas are made up of a group of people who are dislocated or relocated from their homeland. Diasporas maintain a strong bond towards their motherland while living in a foreign land. Diasporas are always nostalgic towards their native culture which is often reflected in theatres and literature. Almost all the languages around the world have at least a minimum influence of Diaspora theory, which is called Diasporic literature or Expatriate Literature. Diasporic Literature is a comprehensive term that encompasses all the literary works written by the authors outside their native country but written about their native culture. When migrant writers' works are deeply rooted in their homeland they are referred to as diasporic writers. Isolation, displacement, nostalgia, and a quest for identity are some key characteristics of diasporic literature; however, it also discourses issues related to the unification or degeneration of cultures. A diasporic text mostly revolves around location; the dislocation or relocation of a group of people and their uneasiness about homelessness and their unlikelihood of going back to their native land.

The immigrants' thoughts are considered to fluctuate between favourable and unfavourable conditions faced by them. Being alienated from their homeland and maybe even away from their family and children, their longing to regain the lost life often culminates in the creation of a new version of the life. These inner conflicts and their outcomes are also addressed by diasporic literature.

English literature has been greatly enriched because of the literary contributions of the Indian Diaspora writers. Contemporary Indian writers through their contributions to English literature have portrayed various issues that are engendered due to diaspora and migration. The issues portrayed include discrimination, relocation, marginalization, hostility, disintegration, racial discrimination, identity crisis, cultural conflict, and many others. The legendary writers like Kamala Markandaya, Mulkraj Anand, Raja Rao, and R. K. Narayan of Indian English literature are well known for their depiction of contemporary Indian life. All of them through their writings had expressed strong perseverance to expose the cold realities of life to bring the desired change in society. Their writings seem to be thriving on themes like Poverty, Partition, Patriotism, Agricultural labourers, Feminism, divisions like East-West, Urban-Rural, Conservative Practices, and Communal differences. Even the postmodern Indian English novelists have also, through their novels addresses Diasporas. But they have diverted from the pioneers and have addressed a new set of themes emerging out of globalization. These emerging themes include but are not limited to a pluralistic society, unethical values, consumerism, crony capitalism, commoditization, etc. This change embraced by the writers is a piece of evidence that Diasporic sensibility keeps changing with time and place.

Kamala Markandaya, a well-known Indian author and journalist who was also a prominent Diasporic novelist through her literary works, raised her voice against various discrimination and marginality prevailing both in homelands and foreign and homelands. She was born in 1924 in an upper-middle-class family in Mysore. Her literary works are known for boldness, freedom, identity, and discrimination. Kamala Markandaya, through her eleven novels, had been identified as one of the renowned and well-established writers of modern India. She migrated from her motherland India to England which is the country of abode. Her writings mostly revolve around the culture, of both countries. From her writings, we can observe that Kamala Makandaya was a victim of both Indian and Western cultures. She had penned down her experiences and had expressed her thoughts through the fictional characters of her novels.

Kamala Markandaya's novel *Nectar in a Sieve* is a classic example through which she brings out the trauma due to the dislocation and disintegration of the fictional character Rukmani's family. Rukmani's family was leading a quiet and peaceful life but it was drastically affected by undesirable

events due to the arrival of a tannery. The village and its calm and peaceful atmosphere were almost destroyed by the arrival of the tannery. The tannery here is a symbol of uninvited power that destroys the life of the village. The village's fertile agricultural land becomes infertile and produces less produce due to contamination from the tannery waste. Though the tannery initially feeds Rukmani's family, later it turns out to be a disaster for them. The tannery, for their expansion, purchases lands of the village at a premium price from the landlords. Because of this Rukmani's family loses the land which they were cultivating for decades. The landlord evicts Rukmani and Nathan from the land which serves as a terrible blow in their life. This unexpected event forces them to migrate from village to city for their livelihood. The migration to the city is not pleasant as they face a lot of hardships. The author here clearly brings out the challenges faced by the common man due to industrialisation. The situation faced by Rukmani and Nathan is a reflection of the life of many poor families that got affected due to industrialisation.

Their lifestyle stoops so low that they had to go to a temple in the evenings anticipating getting a share of free food that is being distributed free. Due to the huge crowd in the temple to their disappointment, they could not get their share of food. Their poor livelihood forces Nathan into sickness. Rukmani even begs the temple priest for food for herself and her husband which is refused for her. They were forced to share her portion of food. Here the author brings out the impact of migration on the life of the poor. They lose their identity and face discrimination in the land they move to.

The female characters in Markandaya's novels are clear victims of inequality, social injustice, and discrimination done by society and family. Rukmani toils hard to feed the poverty struck family. Here the author brings out the character of strong-willed women who will never let their families down. Rukmani's daughter Ira adds further burden to her since she has chased away her husband in the name of infertility.

Due to circumstances, Rukmani's daughter is thrown into prostitution. Later she gives birth to an illegal child. She is abused and ill-treated by her in-laws and is unable to live with her husband. The story ends tragically despite the toil by Rukmini's whole family, including her other. The family fights till the end but still loses at the end. The author describes the discrimination and marginality faced by each character in the story due to industrialisation and migration.

In 1972 Kamala Markandaya wrote the novel *The Nowhere Man* which is based on the theme of racial discrimination. The story revolves around a family that migrates to a foreign land for a better life. The novel brings out the life experiences faced by the family in the foreign land. This is one of the early diasporic novels, portraying the experience of the family that longs for the homeland with nostalgic memories. The protagonist of the novel—Srinivas a spice trader (and his wife) leaves India for England. Laxman and Seshu their two sons both born in England serving in the British army. The family loses one of their sons. Though the family embraced the host country as their own, they are repeatedly made to feel Indians by the host society. They face hostility and feel that they belong nowhere. In the end, the man who goes to London in search of life loses all hopes and becomes nowhere man due to loneliness and other experiences.

Srinivas is dragged between the cultures of homeland and host country. He is racially discriminated against because of his color and demeaned as an immigrant from the East and is isolated in a foreign land. Not just Srinivas but his whole family is marginalized on foreign soil. Though their children were born and brought up in England, they were not accepted as fellow citizens by natives of England but were treated as foreigners. After a series of unfortunate events, Srinivas' life ends in

misery due to the extreme racism of his neighbor extreme racism. The author brings out the marginality forced on the immigrants by the natives of the host country.

The diaspora theory is well written in *The Nowhere Man* through the experiences of the characters of the novel. Srinivas and his family dream of England as a country of tolerance and equality, but the reality turns out to be different. The hatred towards the post-war immigrant community is faced by a huge immigrant community in the host nations. Srinivas after losing his family, finally lands in a new relationship which also proves to be a fragile one. Racist violence enters the life of Srinivas's and his life changes irrevocably. The author's agony towards the marginalized immigrants is seen in this novel.

Kamala Markandaya's *Possession* is another novel that deals with the diaspora. The central character of the novel, Valmiki a boy from a remote Indian village possesses an inborn talent in painting. Lady Caroline Bell who has good knowledge of art identifies the boy's talent. She intends to take Valmiki to England where she plans to provide him painting coaching under the Western tradition. The boy's family is hesitant to send the boy but Lady Caroline can intellectually convince the family. She takes the boy to her native country and admits him to a school to learn painting. The boy somehow loses faith in Caroline due to the series of incidents that happened around his immigration. His mind is pulled towards his homeland. He wants to release himself from the clutches of Caroline and escape from Western culture. The author through her writing brings out Valmiki's anguishes, sorrows, the inner dilemma between his homeland and foreign land. He ultimately succeeds in rejecting Western culture, presumed comfortable living, and lavish lifestyle, and reaches his village. Back in his village, he continues his simple life.

Though Caroline identifies the boy's exceptional talent, she fails to realize the boy's choices. The boy is not able to adapt to the spirit of western art which is based on western cultural and spiritual traditions. The clash between the thoughts of a British aristocratic scion and the simple spirit of an artist is the central theme of the novel. The boy though provided with a western lifestyle and comfort, passes through a period of depression, emotional anxiety, and inner conflict which makes him travel back to his native culture. He breaks away from the clutches of Caroline and returns to his native village in India. The author brings out how the feelings of the boy are suppressed and his struggle to overcome the domination of Caroline who marginalizes him.

The author through the characterisation of the boy brings out the woes, sorrows, conflicts, and confusion of forcefully immigrated individuals from their homeland to a foreign nation. The readers can empathize with the suppression an immigrants' feelings and their struggle to overcome the domination of aristocrats who marginalize them.

The victimization due to East-West encounter is portrayed by another novel *A Handful of Rice* by Kamala Markandaya. The central character vagabond Ravi is striving for "A Handful of Rice" in the city. The novel depicts the East-West encounter on the cultural level through the conflict arising between the modern culture emerged in India due to western Influence against the native Indian spiritual faith.

The crisis surfaces in a government servant Dandekar's family due to his missing wife. Dandekar's wife Sarojini mysteriously goes missing from their house, which brings mental agony to him. Dandekar gets to know that his wife seeks the help of a swamy for the cure of her tumor. Dandekar insists on getting treated her tumor through the scientific method. He is against her for risking her life by relying on faith instead of science. His family finds fault with Dandekar for shifting his faith from spirituality to science. They believe that the change in Dandekar is because of his closeness to a

foreign culture. Dandekar seeks the help of his officers to send the swamy out of his town to save his wife from his influence. Markandaya takes in hand the cultural clash between faith and science as the central theme of the novel. The Indian mind is engrossed with the belief that the English culture is pragmatic and against the Indian culture which is idealistic. Indians also believe that England through colonial supremacy has exploited India. The clash between Eastern values and Western values results in a quest for identity which is on top of the author's thoughts.

By reading through a few novels of Markandaya, it comes to light that Indian diasporic writers express themes of alienation, isolation, and discrimination as common problems faced by a common man in both homeland and foreign countries. The writers have mirrored the own experience they have undergone in the foreign land. Though they have settled in foreign due to various reasons their host lands have treated them as aliens and were marginalized. Characters in these writers' novels are fictional images of themselves.

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